

CERTIFICATE

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O'ZBEKISTONDA TA'LIM-TARBIYA JARAYONIGA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR.MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR MAVZUSIDA RESPUBLIKA
ILMIY ONLINE KONFERENSIYASIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Hasanova D.A

**Different changes in the small intestine in pulmonary fibrosis. The body's response to
experimental pulmonary fibrosis**

**NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN
TAQDIRLANADI**

2022/DEKABR

